

Motives of Tourist Attending Special Events: The case of International Film Festival of Kerala (IFFK)

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates that motives of tourist attending special events. The study, main focuses on special events like International Film Festival of Kerala (IFFK). Special events are key motivators for tourism. While there is a large number literature regard event tourism motivation, this study discuss on the role of motivations is important to maintain high satisfaction level and to meet tourist demands. The present study investigates whether the present motivation factors are considered in different special events. Consequently, it mainly focused on International Film Festival of Kerala organised by Kerala Chalachithra Academy incorporation with cultural and tourism department. The study found that while there may be a difference in the motivations for an attending tourist in the special events.

KEYWORDS: *Special events, Event Tourism, Event Novelty, Mega Event, Film Festival.*

Introduction

Event tourism becomes the fastest branch of tourism through special events. It represents the systematic development planning, marketing, holding of events as tourist attractions. It is regarded as a unique and frequent, create a favorable image for host destination, to generate large media attractions and to expand traditional tourism season and visitors. Special interest tourist more attracted and participating in the large variety of products and experience offered by event tourism. It provides an opportunity to focus the destination's attractions like a museum, heritage buildings, traditions of community, ethnic and cultural landscape. Furthermore, the Special event produces a significant amount of business and economic output to the host places.

Kerala tourism has been conducting diverse events and festivals to promote tourism. Trivandrum has the rich traditional guardian of the temple treasure and heritage values, it attracted by travellers from the around world. Moreover, the International film Festival of Kerala considered being the annual pilgrimage of all serious film lovers across Kerala and even abroad. The IFFK has witnessed social and cultural effects of its rapid economic growth, especially the impact of this growth on contemporary thoughts and discussion of film lovers. Today, IFFK is the Asia largest people participation film festival and attracted to international tourist. During festival days, it attracted the large number of special interest people to host destination. Therefore, this study focused on the analysis of the motives of tourist attending the International Film Festival of Kerala.

According to Watt (1998), 'A Special Events is a one-off happening designed to meet specific needs at any given time. It may define local community events as an activity established to involve the local population in a shared experience to their mutual benefits'. Similarly, "A special event is a onetime or infrequently occurring event outside normal programs or activities of the sponsoring or organising body. To the customer or guest, a special event is an opportunity for leisure, social or cultural experience and choices or beyond everyday experience." (Allen, O'Toole, McDonnell & Harris, 2002: 12) The last definition is the most suitable from the tourism perspective and is the one it uses that in the current paper.

Objectives of the study

1. To find the motives of tourist attending special events
2. To analyse the motives of tourists attending the special events

Hypotheses

H₀ There is no significant difference in the motives of male and female tourist attending special events

Literature review

Motivations to attend special events related to various factors such as connectivity, accessibility, entertainment, performance, attractiveness, event novelty and special interest. In, the study of Schofield (2007) travel motivation to attending special events with motivation dimension related to specific event. Similarly, Perdue et al. (1990) highlighted that Special events enhance the local pride and several leisure times. Another context special event creates a suitable atmosphere for gathering, sharing and experiencing memorable occasions of their life. According to lee at all (2004) events and festivals having powerful cultural aspects are likely to increase in the participation numbers. (Uysal, Backman & Potts, 1991) extracted twelve motive items with five dimensions of motivation were identified. In the recent study of Yolal, Woo, Cetinel, &Uysal (2012) analyses the satisfaction levels of festival attendees in respect to different festival products. The study explored underlying motivating factors for attending festival products. Similarly, he analyses five factors like socialization, excitement, event novelty, escapes, and family togetherness.

(Arcodia, 2013) studies that the attendee motivations with specific reference to musical performances. Special events are emerging themes and uncover gaps in knowledge that need to be addressed by further research. (Egresi& Kara, 2014) argued that market awareness and visitor motivation is extremely significant for tourism promotion and planning. Therefore, the survey put on the motives of visitors attending events. The study followed the variation in the motivations for attending various types of events.

(Tro & Slamar, 2016) examined the motivation for event participation in the situation of event attendees (visitors) and event participants. The study extracted the main event attendance motivation as leisure and entertainment, spending quality time with friends and the cultural offering of events. In addition, the experience has the favourable impact on visitors and participants.

Therefore, in the increasing numbers of study concerned tourist attending motivates. The majority have discussed that motivations of tourist attend special events has been one of the main aspects have attracted increasing attention. The study mainly focused on motivation of tourist attending special events in Kerala.

Research Design and Method

This study is a descriptive nature and the study finds the motives of tourist attending special events with International Film Festival of Kerala. The presented data for the study collected through a structured interview schedule with tourist attending special events. The secondary data were gathered from the official website of Kerala tourism, Kerala Chalachithra Academy and International Film Festival of Kerala, different study report directed by private institutions, journals, books and newspaper.

A review of the literature identifies number of statements about motives of tourist attending special events. The survey instrument was developed from the earlier study from (Baker & Crompton, 2000), (Crompton, Mckay, & Society, 1997), Moghar et al. (1993) and Uysal et al. (1991). It included the interview schedule two part: Part one seeks information about the demographic characteristics such as gender, age, marital status, educational qualification, nationality. Part B: Included 5 motivational dimensions with 19 statements arranged in five Likert Style. A convenience sample of tourist attended in the special events survey with 141 completed data being returned and used for analysis.

Results and discussion

Respondent's Demographic characteristics

Table 1 : Distribution of Sample by their Demographic Characteristics

Demographic profile		IFFK	
		N	%
Gender	Male	116	83.5
	Female	23	16.5
Nationality	Indian	120	85.11
	Foreign	21	14.89
Age	Below 25	37	26.6
	25-34	65	46.8
	35-44	22	15.8
	45 and above	15	10.8
Marital Status	Single	90	64.7
	Married	49	35.3
Education	School Level	4	4.26
	Graduate	58	41.7
	Post Graduate	57	41.0
	Professional	20	14.4
Occupation	Student	40	28.8
	Salaried	46	33.1
	Business	16	11.5
	Professional	37	26.6
	Others	7	4.96

This study chooses 139 respondents were selected from the International Film Festival of Kerala. The respondents attending the International Film Festival of Kerala were low between males and females with the dominant age group being 25

to 34 years (46.8%). In terms of education of the tourists also determines them in the selection of special events. Table 1 shows that 41.7% of the respondents were graduate level. Similarly, the occupation of the tourists has a direct impact on the disposable income and travel behaviour of the person. Table 1 reveals that 33.1% of respondents are salaried employees, 28.8% of tourists are even studying, and 26.6% of respondents are professionals, and 20.57% of the tourists are professional's and 4.96% as others.

To analyse the motives of tourists attending the special events, an independent sample test was used to study difference in the motives of male and female tourist attending special events.

Table 2 : Independent Sample test of Motivational factors

Motivation factors	Male		Female		t value	p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Socialisation	3.27	0.81	3.41	0.68	-0.75	0.77
Excitement	3.91	0.78	3.90	0.66	0.05	2.20
Event Novelty	3.57	0.86	3.59	0.98	-0.13	1.23
Escape	3.17	1.04	3.62	0.74	-1.98	5.06
Family Togetherness	2.57	1.16	2.70	1.07	-0.47	0.53

The male respondents were associated with a socialisation factor $M = 3.27$ ($SD = 0.81$). By comparison, Female ($N = 23$) was associated with numerically smaller than male. To test the hypothesis that the male and female respondents were associated with statistically different mean socialisation factor, an independent sample test was performed. The male respondents given the highest mean scores on excitement and event novelty as the highest mean scores of 3.91 and 3.57 obtained respectively.

The female respondents are given more importance on excitement and escape with score of 3.90 and 3.62 respectively. There is no significant difference in the motives of male and female tourist (p -value is > 0.05) in the five motivational factors. Here the motives of male and female tourist not differentiated.

The study mainly an attempt to understand motives of tourists attending the special events and extend the theoretical aspects and literature on the motivation factors, although the relationship is not significant. Nevertheless, the study highlighted that the motivation factors like excitement, event novelty, escapes are important factors considering by tourist attending special events. In other words, special interest people go on a travel to satisfying their intrinsic and extrinsic desires.

Conclusions

The results of this study give a clear idea about motivational factor closely associated with gender basis. It can be argued that the major findings of this study have a significant role in the effective marketing of destination and competition among the other state. To understanding motivational factors of special event can help to extend the duration of the stay, increasing visitor's satisfaction and enhancing revisit to events and location. There are few studies on dealing with special events in Kerala. It suggested that the approach can be applied to other

special events in Kerala like Kochi Muziris Biennale, Kerala Literature Festival and International Theatre Festival of Kerala. Overall, the study examined motivations to attend a special event at an exploratory stage, further study with large sample and various special events could be given more depth about motives of tourist attending special events.

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